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IMPORTANCE OF ONTOLOGICAL RESEARCH WITHIN THE PEDAGOGY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: Ontology is an important emerging discipline that has the huge potential to improve information organization, management and understanding. It has a crucial role to play in enabling content-based access, interoperability, communications, and providing qualitatively new levels of services on the next generation. The article describes the role of ontology in teaching and pedagogy.

Keywords: Ontology, conceptualization, teaching, pedagogy.

Introduction

Semantic publishing [1,2] can be defined as the activity of enhancing a document (e.g. a journal article) with semantic annotations, providing a way to understand the meaning of the published information and enabling the linking to related documents. Semantic publications offer a better access to both their content and metadata describing the entire documents, their structure, their rhetorical elements and related information. Several ontologies have been created to support this activity in different scholarly domains, e.g., EXPO [3] in the scientific experiments domain, OMDoc as a markup format and data model for Open Mathematical Documents [4], the SWAN ontology for modelling the scientific discourse, developed in the context of building a series of applications for biomedical research [5]. However, the variety of works that describe documents in different domains makes it difficult to choose the best ontology for the annotation of scientific papers, besides the obvious use of Dublin Core Terms¹. Moreover, there are no general conventions or rules on how to use the existing ontologies in semantic publishing. In order to shed light on this variety of works, in this paper

¹ Dublin Core Metadata Element Set, Version 1.1 <http://dublincore.org/documents/2008/01/14/dces/>

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we review the most relevant ontologies for describing scholarly publications and we also present other vocabularies that allow embedding formal metadata in documents using markup languages.

Ontologies for describing documents

One of the earliest works in this direction was the no-longer maintained Document ontology², implemented in the SHOE language. This ontology focuses only on the document type. Some of the documents types defined in this ontology are: Abstract, Letter, Form, Lecture, etc.

The Ontology of Rhetorical Blocks (ORB)³ captures a coarse-grained rhetorical structure of scientific publications, independently of their domain. The ontology models a publication by means of three artefacts: the header, the body and the tail. The header is the part of the publication that models meta-information about the publication, including title, authors, affiliations, publishing venue and abstract. The body is composed by four rhetorical blocks: introduction, methods, results and discussion, according to the IMRAD [7] structure. Finally the tail provides additional meta-information about the paper, related to external references. The tail is represented by two ontological entities: acknowledgments and references.

A recent work that attempts to annotate the entire characteristics of a document is the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies⁴ a set of ontologies that allow describing books and journal articles, citations, bibliographic records, the component parts of documents, and various aspects of the scholarly publication process. This set of ontologies is composed by:

- FaBiO, the FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology, which allows recording and publishing bibliographic records of scholarly documents.
- CiTO[8], the Citation Typing Ontology, which allows characterising citations, both factually and rhetorically.
- BiRO, the Bibliographic Reference Ontology, which allows describing bibliographic records and references, and their compilation into bibliographic collections and reference lists.
- C4O, the Citation Counting and Context Characterization Ontology, which

² <http://www.cs.umd.edu/projects/plus/SHOE/onts/docmnt1.0.html>

³ <http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/hcls/notes/orb/#ontology>

⁴ SPAR, namespace <http://purl.org/spar>

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allows the characterization of bibliographic citations in terms of their number and their context.

- DoCO10, Document Components Ontology, which allows describing the component parts of a document. DoCO imports the Discourse Elements Ontology11 and the Document Structural Patterns Ontology12

- PRO13, the Publishing Roles Ontology, which allows characterising the roles of agents in the publication process.

- PSO14, the Publishing Status Ontology, which allows characterising the publication status of a document at each of the various stages in the publishing process.

- PWO15, the Publishing Workflow Ontology, which allows describing the steps in the workflow associated with the publication of a document.

The scientific discourse has particular characteristics that are not covered by the aforementioned ontologies. Particularly, a scientific discourse has goals, claims, experiments, evaluations and so on. Indeed, the reasoning of the assertion of the scientific document is crucial for scholarly and scientific publishing, in proposing hypotheses and advancing evidence in their support. Several works have been proposed to model the discourse argumentation normally present in scientific articles.

One of the first works to address the modelling of the scholarly discourse was ScholOnto[10]. The ScholOnto ontology provided a small set of conceptual and relational types. The main class of the ontology is the Claim. All claims are owned by an agent, and have some form of justification. Claims assert new relationships with other claims, or between concepts. The work proposed by [11,12] identifies the main components of scientific investigations and construct the Core Information about Scientific Papers (CISP) metadata about the content of papers. The main classes proposed in CISP are: Goal of investigation, Motivation, Object of investigation, Research method, Experiment, Observation, Result and Conclusion. CISP metadata makes use of the ontology of experiments EXPO16[3] as a core ontology. CISP includes eight key classes.

As aforementioned, CISP makes use of EXPO, a very complete ontology about scientific experiments. The aim of this ontology is to provide a controlled vocabulary of scientific experiments. For this purpose EXPO defines over 200 concepts to allow providing a formal description of experiments for efficient

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analysis, annotation and sharing of results. EXPO is able to describe computational and physical experiments, experiments with explicit and implicit hypothesis. EXPO defines general classes including ScientificExperiment, ExperimentGoal, ExperimentTechnology, ExperimentResult, etc.

Inspired by EXPO and CISP metadata, the work described in [13] proposes the Core Scientific Concepts, CoreSCs. The CoreSCs is a scheme built upon eleven categories at the sentence level that allows the automatic recognition of each one of the categories in scientific articles. The CoreSC includes: hypothesis, motivation, goal, object, background, method, experiment, model, observation, result and conclusion. The authors argued that these categories describe the main components of a scientific investigation. The first application of this scheme has been used to automatically annotate papers in Biochemistry and Chemistry.

Other works, such as The Argument Model Ontology¹⁷, use the ‘Toulmin Model of Argument’ [14]. Toulmin proposed a layout containing six interrelated components for analysing arguments: claim, evidence, warrant, backing, qualifier and rebuttal. The Argument Model Ontology models this components through a set of 8 classes and 21 properties.

A very recent work is the one proposed in [15] MicroPublications¹⁸. In this work the authors employ the Toulmin’s model updated by Bart Verheij [16] and then they propose a semantic model of scientific argument and evidence designed for representing the key arguments and evidence in scientific articles. MicroPublications proposes a model to construct an argumentation network linking textual statements and data as evidence for claims. Beyond the works that employ a linguistic model there are other works that are focused on describing the scientific discourse itself and the relations among the claims and hypotheses made by the author of the document.

Ontological Conceptualization

Teachers, students, parents, policymakers, and other professionals care about education as the key to better positions for young and old in a more just society. Educational research is expected to inform scientifically the ongoing debates about good education and learning through life, in particular within the current polarized world (The Politics of Learning Writing Collective, 2017). At the intersection of disciplines such as educational studies, educational psychology, learning sciences, and related developmental, behavioral, social, subject-specific, and organizational

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disciplines, educational research has become an established domain. The great expectations, however, come with recurring concerns about its relevance (e.g., Farley-Ripple et al., 2018; Gutiérrez & Penuel, 2014; Snow, 2016). We see various criticisms, for example, that research findings are not considered useful, applicable, generalizable, or replicable (Broekkamp & van Hout-Wolters, 2007; Kim, 2019; Makel & Plucker, 2014; Vanderlinde & Van Braak, 2010).

The complaints illustrate what we, as educational researchers from Europe and North America, see as a tendency in many quarters of educational research: judging the relevance of research on the basis of its outcomes and its local or lasting societal impact. The same orientation on effects is evident in the reviews of research proposals and publications. Research can have a societal impact, but it is, we argue, not a suitable guiding principle for achieving or judging relevance. Impact is namely a rather empty notion: It focuses on what happens with outcomes, and disregards what research findings are or should be about in the first place. It is possible that research has a major impact but perhaps a contested one. For example, Hattie's (2009) synthesis of meta-analyses has become very popular, but the literature abounds with criticism of his approach and undesirable consequences (Bergeron & Rivard, 2017; Terhart, 2011). Another example is the research on learning styles that has also had a significant societal impact. However, most researchers contest the concept of learning styles and lament the assessment industry founded on it (Kirschner & van Merriënboer, 2013; Pashler et al., 2008). One can also imagine a research project where results are negative or not ready for dissemination. The wisest decision then may be not to try and have an impact on education. With the current focus on impact, one has to be strong in resisting this call as the primary basis for judging relevance—especially if one has promised mountains in the original research proposal [17].

We do agree that our field struggles with a relevance problem, but it is more fundamental than disappointing outcomes or impact. Relevance can be defined as “relation to the matter at hand” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Accordingly, this essay proposes a conceptualization of relevance of educational research in terms of its ontology, that is, in terms of the key matters that our field is about and researchers' relationship with those matters. Our ontological perspective leads us to raise the following questions: What is the nature of learning? What happens and matters when it comes to education in current societies? How do we as educational

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researchers identify, respond to, and intervene in what happens and matters in education and processes of learning throughout life? By asking these questions, we join critical discussions on ontology in our field (e.g., Bang & Vossoughi, 2016; diSessa & Cobb, 2004; O'Connor & Penuel, 2010; Packer & Goicoechea, 2000; Roth, 2018; Säljö, 2002). In line with Barad (2007), we take ontology to include epistemology and axiology, meaning that a consideration of ontology inherently involves questions such as: How do we come to know and what are consequences of knowledge? What values and perspectives do we communicate, and how do we come to these values? An answer to this last question requires that we attend to our particular locations as scholars in social and economic systems, networks of power, history, and other positionings that sociologists of science and critical scholars have noted shape our standpoints in research[18].

We see it as an ethical obligation of our profession to come up with a view on what makes research relevant and worth doing, even when not yet clear how useful findings or products will be or how much impact research will have. As professionals we need to have a proper perspective on the nature and purposes of educational research (cf. Winch, 2001). The conceptualization of relevance that we offer in this essay does not take sides as to what form of research is more relevant; it is not meant to suggest particular research topics or methodologies but to offer an approach for educational scholars to explicitly address the question of what is relevant research. To ground our proposal, the next sections first summarize our ontological claim about the nature of learning and education. We argue that education and learning are specific kinds of historical and moving phenomena and pinpoint what potential harm to relevance we see in the field when not taking this moving nature into account. Inspired by critical perspectives in philosophy and the sociology of science, we propose an approach that we call ontological synchronization. This approach entails adhering to two principles: actuality and generativity, where the first entails staying attuned to what is happening and matters in the present and presence of people, and the second entails staying aware of what future is being suggested for people in settings and societies, including in research.

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